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Geophysical Investigation of Radiometric Data of Igumale and Nsukka, Southern Nigeria for Possible Spots of Radiogenic Heat Generation

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Abstract

Objectives: High-resolution aero-radiometric data of Igumale and Nsukka of Southeastern Nigeria, were used in this study to ascertain the local proportion levels of uranium (U), thorium (eTh) and potassium (K). **Methods:** Obtained data were grid and subjected to Geosoft analysis using Oasis Montaj Package. **Findings:** The analysis's findings showed that the potassium concentrations vary from 0.00% to 0.6%. The average thorium concentration was 13.6 ppm, having value spanning from 4.3 to 22.9 ppm. The uranium concentration level varies between 0.5 to 7.0 ppm with average value of 20.86572 ppm. There is a very clear discountunity seen in the middle of the research area trending north to south allowing the passage of low concentration of all three radioactive substances towards the southeastern region. The ternary map revealed radioactive mineral compositions which are exceedingly high in the southeastern part and associated with Esh and Arish formation resulting from felsic volcanic rock deposits greater than the usual average value of radioactive materials a reliable geothermal energy source in the environment. The low concentration combined effect of the three radioelement falls within longitude 7°20' to 7°40' and found in areas within the false bedded sandstone, coal and shale (FSS), sandstone (ESS), coal, sanstone and shale (LCM) formation where as high concentration combined effect is located within latitude 6°30' and 6°47' and longitude 7°47' and 8°00' are associated with Esh and Arish formation. Spot for RHP is seen to be very high in the north western and extending towards the south eastern part of the study area whereas low radiogenic heat production (RHP) is evident at the boundary between Nsukka and Igumale central part of study area trending NS between longitude 7° 30' and 7° 60'. **Novelty:** The research revealed spot of high RHP which will guide geoscientists, miner and investors in choosing the optimal locations for installing an exploratory well to harness high generated heat.

Keywords: Aeroradiometric; Radioelements; Igumale-Nsukka; Total count map; Ternary map; Radiogenic heat production

1 Introduction

The Igumale-Nsukka lithology consists of the Nsukka and Mamu formations of the Anambra basin that harbors significantly some abundant economical deltaic deposits of carbonaceous shales, silt shales, and coals silt stones. Most of the shales were laminated and alternated with sandstones which are raw materials for manufacturing glasses while the lateritic sandstones in the study were used for various construction purposes such as road, buildings and bridges⁽¹⁾. The Ajali sandstones have clayey shales formally used for pottery and glazed tiles in the ceramic industry. The economic importance of coal resources in the area is not ignored as it has a future prospect for industries like iron, steel, and cement industries, raw material for chemical industries and cooking coal. The alternation of these shales and sandstones in the study area might have increased and provided a favorable condition for petroleum accumulation considering other factors like depth/thickness of the sedimentary basin, geothermal gradient and radiogenic heat production zones. Notwithstanding these advantages, the broader national energy challenge remains constrained. Despite that Nigeria possesses substantial oil, gas, hydro, solar, and other resource reserve has the capacity to produce 12522 MW of electricity from its existing plants. However, on most days, it can only dispatch about 4500 MW,⁽²⁾ which is insufficient for an increasing population exceeding 200 million⁽³⁾. This persistent shortfall in energy generation has intensified interest in alternative, clean, renewable, and reliable energy sources capable of supporting long-term economic growth and reducing greenhouse-gas emission. Recent geothermal studies using borehole temperature logs, heat-flow assessments, and basin thermal modeling indicate that several Nigerian sedimentary basins, including the Anambra Basin, possess geothermal conditions favorable for low to medium heat energy development. This geophysical information triggered the search for geothermal spots for heat generation, radiogenic heat production, demarcation and alteration of structures, rock alteration, concentration of hydrocarbon, and radiometric minerals.

Airborne geophysical method especially high-resolution magnetic, gravity, and radiometric survey have proven effective for mapping subsurface structures, estimating geothermal gradients, detecting Curie depths, and identifying radioactive mineral concentrations. Airborne gamma-ray spectrometry has become an increasingly important tool in geological mapping and land-use studies. Advances in airborne radiometric and magnetic techniques have enhanced subsurface mapping across Nigerian basins, enabling improved detection of lithological boundaries, structural discontinuities, radiometric mineralization zones, and radiogenic heat-producing units⁽⁴⁾. These results aim to support mineral exploration, environmental radiation assessment, and the long-term pursuit of sustainable geothermal energy development in the Igumale–Nsukka region. However, despite its seismic, thermal, and lithological attributes that make it a favorable target for geothermal assessment, no study has examined the radiometric properties or evaluated the potential for radiogenic heat production, radioactive mineralization, or structural alteration using aeroradiometric data in the study area, and this information limits the understanding of the geochemical energy potential and evolution of the region.

Since sedimentary sand-clay terrigenous rocks are radioactive and sorb thorium and uranium well⁽⁵⁾, our study area, which is a sedimentary basin might have deposits of radioactive elements. This study employs the interpretation of high-resolution airborne radiometric data to quantify radioelement concentrations, delineate structural and lithological variations, and identify zones with enhanced radiogenic heat production. The result will provide new insights in the geothermal viability and economic prospects of the Igumale–Nsukka area while aiding in the ongoing efforts to diversify sustainable energy sources in Nigeria.

1.1 Geology and Location of the Area

Nsukka is a sedimentary basin covered by six main geological formations found in the Anambra Basin between Coniacian and Paleocene-aged rock having a total surface area of about 6,050 km², and located within longitudes 7°00' and 8°00' and latitudes 6°30' and 7°00'. According to⁽⁶⁾, the deposited rock formations are divided into four namely the Mamu, Ajali Sandstone, the Nsukka and the Imo Shale formation. Over 3,965 m thickness of sediments, consisting of limestone, coal, shales, and sandstones are discovered to have been deposited in this formation. Most of these deposited sediments have major economic significance and might possess traces of glass sands, reserves of coal, ironstones, and substantial possibility for natural oil and gas. The region's highest elevation point is approximately 521 meters; however, the lowland's elevations falls below 281 meters above sea level⁽⁷⁾. The area has fertile soil that supports a thriving rural agriculture with multiple extended and cone-shaped hills divided by dry and rainy valley.

Igumale is a town in Benue State located 150 kilometers away from the state capital Makurdi. It is the headquarters of Ado Local Government Area headquarters of Benue State. Igumale is found within the lower Benue Trough, which has a usual structure of cracks and lines with prevalent NE-SW direction patterns and intrusive bodies with varying thickness and distinct magnetizing directions, indicating that these intrusive bodies came from the same underlying mantle material and were probably absorbed at several polar periods. The four main physiographic provinces where sediments were deposited during this time span are found in the Escarpment, the Plateau, the Cross River swamps, and the Anambra lowlands. The mean temperature

of the area ranges from 26.7 to 28.9 °C having an average lowest temperature ranging between 18.3 - 21.1 °C. The daily maximum temperatures are observed between March and April, whereas daily minimum temperatures happen between December and January. The earliest sea transgression took place in the middle of the Albian and was primarily limited to the Benue Valley and southeastern Nigeria. The Abakaliki-Benue trough was created during this tectonic era, occurring in three cycles: the Asu River cycle, the Ezeaku cycle and the Agwu cycle. The Ezeaku cycle's regression phase evolved and formed the lower Benue region's Igumale Division's middle Turonian shales and limestone. According to ⁽⁸⁾, Igumale shale is silty clay and is not appropriate to be used as a foundation core, subbase, or filler material in the construction of roads. A map given in Figure 1 depicts the geological lithology of the research area.

Fig 1. Map showing the geology of the study area.

2 Methodology

The airborne radiometric data were collected from the Nigerian Geological Survey Agency (NGSA). The collection of data was obtained by FUGRO-Air Services on behalf of the Nigerian government from 2004 to 2009. The high-resolution aero-

radiometric (HRAR) data of sheets 287 (Nsukka) and 288 (Igumale) containing the three radioelements were obtained with flight heights of 80. The flight line and tie line spacing intervals are 500 m, and 2000 m respectively. This data reveals more resolution than the earlier 1975–1978 data, whose data acquisition flight heights were 2 km, with a NE–SW trending tie line interval of 2 km. When compared to the flight height of 2 km utilized during 1975–1978 survey of this potential field data, the higher resolution data applied 500 m, 2000 m flight line intervals and 80 m flight height employing a flight line tilt angle of 135° and tie-line angle trend of 45° demonstrated a considerable increase in the resolution of the data. Oasis Montaj Geosoft software was used in the analysis. Area of 55 × 55 km² for each of the sheets has total count data of 305556 on a 1:100,000 scale, so the entire area surveyed is 6,050 km².

2.1 Radiometric method

Gravimetry, magnetometry, borehole logging, geoelectrical, radiometric, and seismic techniques are commonly employed in geophysical approaches. The radiometric method entails the measurement of ionizing radiation (α, β, γ) emitted from naturally occurring radioactive substances in rocks and soils. In the field, a spectrometer, which is connected to a scintillation detector, is utilized to capture gamma rays and their respective energies. Although natural radionuclide can potentially release gamma rays having energy range of zero to 3 meV, the survey primarily focuses on the energy range of 0.2 to 3 meV. Spectral peaks detected are correlated with the elements potassium, uranium and thorium. The total count (TC) reflects the frequency at which these aforementioned elements are tallied. These measurements, contingent upon the measurement surroundings and geology, unveil the radioactivity of strata varying from a few centimeters to one meter. Dilapidated rocks are often found in close proximity to the earth's surface. Weathering causes the frequent liberation of thorium through the dissolution of minerals, which could subsequently be retained in clays, iron or Titanium oxides or hydroxides. Due to its reactivity, uranium can be effortlessly extracted from its natural reservoirs. The occurrence of uranium may manifest in various forms like mineral oxide and silicates namely uranorthorite and uraninite, which can be found in rocks. Uranium may also exist in small quantity in other minerals or found along the grain boundaries⁽⁹⁾.

This method is widely employed in direct search for Uranium, mapping the geology of an area to distinguish different rock types, since a number of rocks exhibit inherently radioactive properties. Nonetheless, the natural response from rocks is confined to a depth order of approximately half a meter, owing to the inability of gamma rays to penetrate further. This technique is capable of mapping solely the near-surface, which is especially beneficial in the field of agriculture, where different soil types can be mapped. Moreover, radiometric instruments possess the capacity to identify faults that serve as channels for the release of radiation in the form of radon gas to the surface. Additionally, these instruments are capable of determining the actual concentration of radioactive elements, thus enabling the quantification of rocks or drill-core in situ, an approach that is potentially faster than conducting assays in a geochemical laboratory. Radiometric instruments are also useful for monitoring contamination in soil resulting from nuclear reactor leakage, the presence of radioactive radon gas, which is a precursor to earthquakes, and the progress of radioactive tracers utilized to define the rate of flow of liquids. The radiometric dating is a breakdown process in which various elements emit atomic particles, element that undergoes this process is said to be disintegrated or decayed.

Radioactivity is the process by which an atom that is unstable transforms into an atom that is stable as its nucleus undergoes decay. By observing the gamma rays released when isotopes of radioactive materials decay, gamma ray spectrometry is a geophysical method used to determine the quantities of these gamma rays and detected radio-elements such as potassium, uranium, and thorium. The naturally detected gamma radiation originates from several rock types, with those that contain potassium and uranium exhibiting the highest activity, such as granites, shales, and clays, as well as from radon gas in the atmosphere, which is a byproduct of uranium. Artificial sources encompass the detection of leakage from reactors and isotopes used as tracers, which possess energy levels much higher than those of natural sources. Potassium isotope of (40K), Uranium isotopes of (235U, 238U) and Thorium isotope of (232Th) represent the primary natural radioactive elements that comprise the earth's crust. The electromagnetic spectra known as gamma radiation have a distinct and unique energy (E), wavelength (λ), and frequency (f) and propagate at the speed of light (c). The relationship between these variables is expressed as equation (1).

$$E = hf = \frac{hc}{\lambda} \quad (1)$$

Decay chain series: The process of decay chain involves the sequential disintegration of discrete radioactive decay products. This chain of transformations follows the principles of radioactive decay which expresses the decline in the amount of unstable nuclei of atoms over time is expressed mathematically as equation (2)⁽¹⁰⁾:

$$N_t = N_o e^{-\lambda t} \quad (2)$$

where N_t is the number of atoms following their initial amount of decay with time t (s) is denoted by N_0 and λ signifies the decaying rate of the unstable nuclei (s^{-1}). $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (s), succinctly stated is the time it takes for N_0 to decrease by half or by 50% is an element's half-life.

$$T_{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{0.693}{\lambda} \quad (3)$$

The process of disintegration of an unstable nucleus remains independent of any supplementary physical factors. The product of λ and N yields the level of activity (in Becquerels) of the unstable nuclei⁽¹⁰⁾.

2.2 Radiometric Data Processing and Methodology

The radiometric information utilized had undergone preliminary preprocessing prior to handling by Fugro-Aero services. The fundamental aim is to carry out the initial processing of the radiometric data to guarantee the rectification of the measured radiometric data in connection with extraneous impacts not pertaining to geologically related sources. The majority of the initial methodology processes were implemented by the data acquisition survey company to guarantee the accuracy and quality of the collected data. The initial methodologies comprise of amalgamating signals from diverse sources, verifying the measured data, as well as verifying against absent or false data values. The radiometric data underwent subsequent corrections, including general correction of background noise, terrain clearance and variation correction⁽¹¹⁾. The latter is attributable to non-geologic sources like cosmic rays, instrument background noise and atmospheric radons. Additional corrections, such as height correction, spectral smoothing and data labeling, were made in the field. Ternary images, as well as concentration maps of thorium (Th), potassium (K) and uranium (U), were generated to facilitate the mapping of hydrothermally altered zones and to aid in the interpretation of radiometric signatures linked to different lithologies. A study by⁽¹²⁾ noted that an increase in K and a reduction in eTh are indicative of a shift in the environments of an ore deposit. The generation of each of the three radioelement' concentration was accomplished through the utilization of the Oasis Montaj software, wherein the two data sheets were imported in geosoft x-y-z format. The longitude and latitude are expressed as x- and y- coordinates respectively, while the z- coordinate represents the radioactive substances in their appropriate units. The radioactive substances were classified into uranium (consisting of two datasheets), thorium (consisting of two datasheets), and potassium (consisting of two datasheets).

The Grid and Image Geosoft extension (GX) utilized the software's blending approach to combine the data sheets and generate the concentration map for each radioactive element. The Total Count Map, which represents the collective impacts maximum energy of the three radioactive materials, was generated by blending together the concentration maps of potassium, uranium and thorium. Moreover, the Ternary Image plug-in for Grid and Image GX by Oasis Montaj Software was used to create the Ternary map of the study area which is a composite image of colors. The Ternary Image plug-in was employed in order to assign primary colors to each radioactive element. Thorium was denoted as green, Potassium was assigned red color whereas Uranium was assigned blue color. The proportions of these colors were regulated based on the measured concentration of the radioelement K, Th, and U. Prior to combining the components into a single image, histogram equalization was applied to improve the brightness and produce the best color variation. This method of color presentation, utilizing primary colors; red, green, and blue color for K, Th, and U respectively is a standard practice in the display of gamma-ray spectrometric data⁽¹³⁾. The estimation of radiogenic heat production (RHP) of the area involves; identifying the types of rock unit across each of the areas from the geological map (Figure 1) of the study area and this was multiplied by its average rock density, (Table 1), estimating the average concentrations of the isotopes (C_K , C_U , and C_{Th}) by vertically tiling the three radioelements, create a database for them, and profiled each area in the N-S direction across the rock identified using Grid profile in the Grid and Image GX of Oasis Montaj. After which the RHP of each of the areas was computed in accordance with the concentration (C) of the respective elements using Eq. (4) which is primarily concerned with the decaying of radioactive isotopes of ^{232}Th , ^{238}U and ^{40}K ⁽¹⁴⁾.

$$Q = \rho(0.035C_K + 0.097C_U + 0.026C_{Th}) \quad (4)$$

where Q is radiogenic heat production in μWm^{-3} , ρ is average rock density (kg m^{-3}), C_K is the average concentration of K by % weight, C_U and C_{Th} are the average concentrations of U and Th (ppm), respectively. The constant value for U (0.097) almost triples the constant values for K (0.035) and Th (0.026); indicating the major role that U plays in producing heat compared with the two other radioelements.

Table 1. Results of Radiogenic Heat Production

S/N	Locations	Longitude (E°)	Latitude (N°)	K (%) Mean	Th (ppm) Mean	U (ppm) Mean	Radiogenic Heat, Q ($\mu W m^{-3}$)
1	SW Nsukka	7.1	6.6	0.195	11.958	2.803	1.473
2	SS Nsukka	7.3	6.6	0.156	12.015	2.835	1.481
3	SE Nsukka	7.4	6.6	0.111	6.691	1.065	0.702
4	SW Igunmale	7.6	6.6	0.170	14.484	3.909	1.902
5	SS Igunmale	7.8	6.6	0.230	12.768	3.636	1.730
6	SE Igunmale	7.9	6.6	0.420	15.758	4.202	2.078
7	W- Nsukka	7.1	6.8	0.200	12.908	3.134	1.615
8	C-Nsukka	7.2	6.8	0.190	13.081	3.208	1.643
9	E-Nsukka	7.4	6.8	0.124	7.717	1.409	0.854
10	W-Igunmale	7.6	6.8	0.159	12.748	3.332	1.649
11	C-Igunmale	7.7	6.8	0.232	15.543	4.760	2.182
12	E-Igunmale	7.9	6.8	0.350	15.013	4.106	2.000
13	NW Nsukka	7.1	6.9	0.204	14.226	3.715	1.841
14	NN Nsukka	7.2	6.9	0.182	14.392	3.714	1.850
15	NE Nsukka	7.4	6.9	0.129	12.678	2.512	1.443
16	NW Igunmale	7.6	6.9	0.099	8.998	2.083	1.097
17	NN Igunmale	7.7	6.9	0.192	18.013	5.525	2.524
18	NE Igunmale	7.9	6.9	0.226	12.991	4.086	1.853
	Minimum			0.099	6.691	1.065	0.702
	Maximum			0.42	18.013	5.525	2.524
	Average			0.198	12.888	3.335	1.662

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Potassium Distribution, Concentration and Lithology

The potassium (K) concentration level represented in a map (Figure 2) reveals distinct levels of potassium concentrations with values ranging from 0.03-0.45% marking the lithological heterogeneity. Low-potassium zones (0.03-0.10%) dominate the central north-south part (Umuabo-Orokam-Ukana) and are characteristic of mature evaporitic sedimentary successions with inherently low K-bearing mineral content. Moderate K concentrations (0.11-0.27%) contains quantities of mixed chemical sedimentary shale-sandstone assemblages, while high K zones (0.27-0.45%) occur along the eastern and western boundaries of the basin and correlate with felsic igneous intrusions and hydrothermally altered terrains⁽¹⁵⁾. These observations are primarily attributed with the typical radiometric potassium signatures of granitic and amphibolitic units (0.3-1.5%), as well as alteration and significantly related K enrichment in rock formations documented in comparable Nigerian and Indian basins⁽¹⁶⁾.

The spatial clustering of high-K anomalies near intrusive bodies further supports the interpretation that these areas are indicators of heat sources which have experienced potassium-metasomatism associated with hydrothermal alterations which is an established mechanism for radiogenic enrichment in felsic terrains. Recent radiometric studies noted similar K enrichment trends in geothermal fields of West Africa and the Indian Shield⁽¹⁷⁾, supporting the lithological and geothermal relevance of the observed anomalies.

3.2 Thorium Variability and Structural Significance

Thorium concentrations vary from 4.3–21.2 ppm (Figure 3), forming three distinct anomaly zones (high, intermediate and low concentration zones). The low-thorium concentration (LTHC) level varies from 4.3 to 7.8 ppm, trending north to south through the central basin axis between longitudes 7°15' and 7°40', corresponds to detrital sandstone, greywacke, and basic

Fig 2. Map of potassium concentration.

igneous substrates. LThC formed a demarcation pushing the high and intermediate thorium concentration to the western and eastern part and creating a boundary like structure in the center of the area. These low values fall within or slightly above global average Th concentrations for these lithologies (2-6 ppm). Intermediate Th concentrations (9.2-16.7 ppm) reflect transitional lithologies comprising shale, gneiss, schist, and intermediate igneous rocks, consistent with average Th values for metamorphic terrains.

High-thorium zones (17.8-21.2 ppm), which intensify in the western and eastern segments, exceed typical crustal averages (10-12 ppm) and are indicative of acidic-intermediate igneous rocks and hydrothermally altered zones. The alignment of these anomalies with prominent lineaments and structural discontinuities suggests fault-controlled enrichment which the Benue Trough⁽¹⁸⁾, Indian Precambrian, and Nubian Shield basins are widely known for⁽¹⁶⁾. These radiometric structural correlations affirm that thorium enrichment within the study area is strongly controlled by lineament fracture that allows the infiltration of thorium fluid and post-depositional alteration⁽¹⁹⁾.

3.3 Uranium Concentration and Mineralization Potential

The map of uranium concentration (Figure 4) shows values ranging between 0.5-7.0 ppm and displays the spatial patterns observed for thorium. Low-U zones (0.5-1.6 ppm) characterize the central sedimentary zones, whereas High U concentrations (4.2-7.0 ppm) in the northwest and eastern zones correspond to granite, schist, and other felsic lithologies. These values exceed the typical uranium levels of average crustal rocks (2-3 ppm) and approach concentrations reported in uranium-enriched granitic and metamorphic provinces of Brazil, India, and Sudan⁽²⁰⁾. The co-occurrence of high U and Th with mapped intrusive bodies supports the interpretation of localized uranium enrichment and lithologically controlled mineralization. The presence of intrusive complexes and shale-hosted uranium indicators in the eastern region further validates the potential for uranium accumulation, consistent with previous studies in sedimentary basins of northern Nigeria and southern India.

3.4 Ratio maps of Radioelements

Radiometric ratios of radioelements are essential tools for identifying lithological variations and hydrothermal alteration zones because they measure the relative enrichment or depletion of radioelements over another with differing geochemical behaviors.

Fig 3. Map of equivalent of Thorium concentration.

Fig 4. Map of uranium equivalent concentration.

Potassium (K), uranium (U), and thorium (Th) respond differently to weathering, metasomatism, and hydrothermal processes, making their ratios effective alteration indicators⁽²¹⁾. Hydrothermal fluids commonly mobilize and concentrate K-bearing minerals (e.g., illite, sericite, adularia), whereas Th is deficient but remains relatively immobile due to its low solubility and tendency to remain in minerals such as monazite and zircon⁽²²⁾.

3.4.1. K/Th Ratio Map

The K/Th ratio is particularly sensitive to potassic alteration. Classical work documented unaltered lithologies having K/Th ratios in the range of 0.17–0.20 %/ppm⁽¹⁰⁾. More recent radiometric characterization studies similarly confirm that K-enriched alteration zones typically exceed background values by 200–600%, while hydrothermal depletion of Th drives K/Th ratios to values below 0.05 % ppm⁽⁴⁾. In the present study, the K/Th ratio map (Figure 5) identifies multiple anomalous zones with values ≤ 0.03 % ppm, significantly below the global unaltered threshold and therefore indicative of hydrothermal K enrichment. These anomalies occur prominently around latitude 8°00' (NW) and 7°30' (SW) of the study area, represented by pink color shades. The spatial coincidence of these anomalies with lithological patterns altered hydrothermally comprises sandstone, shale; mudstone, limestone, black shale, and siltstone are notably seen around Akpatebe, Ogbo-Uvuru, and Owele⁽²²⁾. Quantitatively, the identified K/Th anomalies exceed the deviation expected for natural sedimentary heterogeneity, aligning instead with alteration-associated enrichment typically reported for basin-hosted hydrothermal systems worldwide⁽²⁰⁾. Thus, the results show strong internal and external validity.

Fig 5. Map showing K/eTh of the area.

3.4.2. eU/eTh Ratio Map

Ratios of radioactive elements are valuable measures of litho-geochemical importance for distinguishing fluid rock interaction, and redox-controlled mobile Uranium (U) whereas Thorium (Th) remains immobile. U is redox-sensitive and more mobile under oxidizing conditions, therefore, elevated eU/eTh values often reflect U concentration an accumulation of organic-rich sediments or paleo-fluid circulation. The eU/eTh ratio map in Figure 6 effectively delineates boundaries that separate the overlying sedimentary formations from the Precambrian basement. Global radiometric datasets show that Precambrian crystalline rocks typically exhibit eU/eTh ratios between 0.10 and 0.25, while sedimentary units, especially shales and carbonaceous mudstones, commonly range from 0.30 to 0.80⁽²³⁾.

The Western part between longitudes 7°10' and 7°40' shows very low eU/eTh ratios ranging from 0.093 to 0.173 ppm is consistent with crystalline or weakly altered basement rocks whereas Eastern sector (longitudes 7°30'–8°00') exhibits higher ratios (0.322–0.360 ppm), corresponding to sedimentary units enriched in uranium-bearing organic matter and clays. These values fall within the global and regional ranges reported for Nigerian sedimentary^{(21), (23)}, validating the interpretation that the eU/eTh anomalies represent lithological transitions rather than instrument noise or processing artefacts. The quantitative statistical treatment applied to the five variables (eU, eTh, K, eU/K, and K/eTh) corroborates the spatial consistency between high-ratio domains and mapped sedimentary units. The negative (lower-bound) radiometric concentrations recorded in Table 1 correspond to deep blue cells in Figure 6 and are characteristic of low-U basement terrains. In contrast, the red–pink anomalies align with sedimentary-hosted radiometric enrichment consistent with regional geological models.

Fig 6. Map showing U/eTh of the area.

3.5 Ternary Map

The integrated ternary radiometric map (Figure 7), derived from the composite concentrations of K, eTh, and eU, provides an integrated lithogeochemical perspective that enhances the discrimination of lithological boundaries, alteration zones, and structural features within the study area. In ternary radiometric mapping, bright (white) tones typically reflect felsic and highly evolved lithologies enriched in all three radioelements, whereas dark zones correspond to radioelement-poor rocks such as quartz-rich sandstones, magnetite-bearing units, carbonaceous sediments, or mafic compositions (10;13, 21]. This fundamental behavior is consistent with the patterns observed in the present study. The region bounded by latitudes 6°30'–6°47' and longitudes 7°47'–8°00' shows the brightest (white) pixels, indicating simultaneous enrichment in K, eTh, and eU. These anomalies correspond to the Esh and Arish Formations, comprised of shale, black shale, siltstone, sandstone, and limestone. Globally, felsic to intermediate sedimentary and metamorphosed units enriched in K-feldspar and clay minerals commonly exhibit ternary high-intensity clusters, with typical ranges of K > 2%, Th > 12 ppm, and U > 3 ppm⁽²¹⁾. Although absolute values in the current dataset are lower due to sedimentary dilution, the spatial clustering is consistent with moderated felsic affinity and diagenetic concentration processes documented in comparable sedimentary basins⁽¹⁴⁾.

The magenta zones, characterized by high K and eU but relatively depleted eTh, suggest selective enrichment of K-bearing and U-absorbing minerals during hydrothermal or diagenetic alteration. This diagnostic colour signature has been reported

Fig 7. Ternary map showing the distribution of the three radioelements in the area; red color for Potassium, blue color for Uranium and green color for Thorium.

in altered granitic and shale-dominated terrains where U is mobilized and adsorbed along clay-rich layers⁽¹³⁾. Conversely, orange-yellow zones, which represent high K and eTh but low eU, match the behaviour of intermediate-felsic sedimentary rocks containing resistant Th-bearing minerals (e.g., monazite, zircon) but lacking significant U fixation capacity. The dark to black regions indicate low composite radioelement abundance and occur dominantly between longitudes 7°20'–7°40', coinciding with the False-Bedded Sandstone (FSS), Eastern Stone Sandstone (ESS), and Lower Coal Measures (LCM). These units, belonging to the Nsukka and Ajali Formations, contain quartz-rich sandstones, carbonaceous shale, pyrite, limonite, and hematite, all of which produce subdued radiometric signals⁽²¹⁾. Similar dark ternary responses have been documented in coal-bearing and ferruginous sandstone sequences in other West African basins and are widely associated with low radioelement retention capacity⁽¹³⁾. The alignment of these dark anomalies with mapped lineaments, fractures, and boundary faults suggests that structural permeability facilitated downward migration of radioelement-depleted fluids, consistent with modern mapping in sedimentary-basement transition zones⁽¹⁴⁾.

Thorium-rich zones (green pixels) dominate the western sector and show an N–S trend consistent with the distribution of resistate mineral-bearing sandstones and consolidated shale units. The uranium-rich signatures (blue pixels) trending from the northeast to southeast, align with Igunmale, Omanze, Agala, Eha-Amufu, Obogu, Egedegede, Emezu, and adjoining localities. These areas coincide with the ANsh shale-limestone units, clay-rich, organic, and carbonate matrices known to have high Uranium concentrate through sorption and redox trapping. The higher values of eU and eTh these regions are comparable with global benchmarks for shale-limestone systems, typically averaging Th between 5 and 20 ppm and U from 2 to 7 ppm⁽²¹⁾. The correlation between high U-Th zones and elevated magnetic susceptibility further supports the presence of intrusive bodies or hydrothermally altered substrates—an observation consistent with previous aeromagnetic interpretations in the region⁽¹³⁾. The ternary map therefore provides a robust, multivariate confirmation of lithology, alteration, and structural influence in the area. Its lithology is in high agreement with global radiometric signatures of sedimentary to basement transition zones, supporting the validity of the radiometric interpretations, the inferred lithological boundaries, and the presence of potential heat-producing radiogenic zones.

3.6 Radiogenic Heat Production

The combined enrichment of K, eTh, and eU across the eastern and western parts of the study area signifies the presence of radiogenic heat-producing lithologies, particularly felsic intrusions and hydrothermally altered rocks. These units are known to generate significant radiogenic heat through decay of U, Th, and K, an essential characteristic for identifying geothermal targets. Recent investigations using airborne radiometrics for geothermal assessments in West Africa and India have shown that areas with similar K-Th-U enrichment patterns exhibit elevated heat flow and shallow Curie depths^{(17), (20)} The radiometric anomalies identified in this study, combined with the structural complexity and adequate basin thickness, strongly suggest that the Igumale–Nsukka region contains promising zones for geothermal resource development. Additionally, high-U and high-Th zones highlight areas of potential economic interest for radioactive mineral exploration and environmental radiation surveys.

The findings of the examination of the radiogenic heat values for each region in the area are summarized in Table 1, which also includes the estimated values of RHP using Eq. (4) and the mean concentration values of the three radioactive elements for each area. Table 1 and Figure 8 indicates that the center region trending N-S between longitudes 7° 30' and 7° 60' has the lowest RHP ($0.702\mu Wm^{-3}$), while the northwestern region has the highest RHP ($2.524\mu Wm^{-3}$). Areas with lowest value of RHP are associated with false bedded sandstone with coal and shale whereas areas with high RHP anomalous correspond to areas that are lithologically consistent with shale and mudstone which is known to have the highest 238U and 232Th concentration and are long-lived isotopes of interest in radioactive decay in the earth's crust⁽²⁴⁾.

The results also revealed some variations in the RHP values in rocks of the same types but in different locations/areas, might result from the irregularity due to the variations in the geochemical behaviors of K, Th, and U during the metamorphism process, which determines the distribution of the natural radioelements⁽²⁵⁾. Orukpa, Ichamma, and Orokam etc in the North western Igumale with high values of RHP have high uranium and thorium contents which show that the high heat is as a result of the abundance of uranium and the thorium in these particular areas. These areas are, therefore, considered hotspots for geothermal energy because of the high values of radiogenic heat production. The contour map of the RHP of the area (Figure 8) presents areas with high radiogenic heat production denoted with HRHP and low radiogenic heat production denoted with LRHP. In Fig.7 where the three radioelemnets have low concentration is also marked as areas where we have low generation of radiogenic heat in the study area. Hence the presence of high concentration of radioactive isotopes increases the radiogenic heat production of an area.

Fig 8. Radiogenic heat production map of the area.

4 Conclusion

Quantitative interpretation of aero radiometric data of Nsukka-Igumale has been successfully carried out using a variety of algorithms, techniques and software tools to effectively characterize and draw forth new geological insights on the radioactive mineralization and radiogenic heat production to delineate lithological boundaries, characterize radioelement distribution, and reveal new into radioactive mineralization. Knowledge about the lithological boundaries gives important clues about mineralization zone potential and radioactive element concentration of the study area. The spatial patterns of K, eTh, and eU clearly reveals major geological structures previously masked by sedimentary overburden, including fault-controlled discontinuities and alteration zones. These findings provide a more refined litho-structural framework which will aid the understanding of mineral potential of the area. The identified high-thorium-concentration (HThC) zones present notable prospects for industrial applications of high-temperature ceramic materials, advanced optical, aerospace components and targets for future rare-metal exploration. Similarly, high-uranium-concentration (HCU) zones exhibit promising potential for low-carbon energy generation. When responsibly developed, these areas could support nuclear-fuel which will serve as a good source of electricity production and strategic energy systems. However, the study emphasizes that unauthorized uranium exploration poses serious health and environmental hazards; therefore, any development must incorporate robust radiological monitoring, controlled mining methods, and strict regulatory compliance.

The ternary radiometric map proved highly effective for imaging lithological boundaries and correlating radiometric signatures with mapped geological units. The observed alignment of K-rich zones with alteration fronts underscores the potential for hydrothermal system mapping and highlights areas suitable for industrial potassium extraction and other value-added uses such as glass production, detergents, dyes, and specialty chemical manufacturing. Nonetheless, high potassium and uranium concentrations at the eastern margin warrant environmental-impact assessment due to potential risks from radon emission, radioactive dust, and groundwater contamination. This research also produced the first integrated radiometric concentration, ratio, ternary, and radiogenic-heat maps of the Nsukka–Igumale area. The high-heat-production anomaly identified in the northwestern part of Igumale marks a significant geothermal prospect with potential for pilot-scale geothermal exploration or hybrid renewable-nuclear energy development. These results provide a guiding dataset for geoscientists, mining companies, policymakers, and energy-sector stakeholders to make informed decisions on resource evaluation and land-use planning.

The dataset will serve as a guide in carrying out targeted ground radiometric and geochemical surveys in the HThC and HCU zones to validate airborne anomalies and quantify ore grades. Also environmental baseline studies must precede any uranium or thorium exploration to mitigate ecological and health risks. Geothermal assessment wells are recommended in the northwestern Igumale heat-production zone to evaluate subsurface temperature gradients and reservoir properties. Structural mapping and geotechnical investigations should be expanded along the north–south radiometric discontinuity to better understand fluid pathways, mineralization controls, and fracture permeability. Integration with remote-sensing and magnetic datasets is encouraged to refine alteration zoning and support mineral-system modeling. The result of this study demonstrate significant radioactive-mineral and geothermal potential in the Nsukka–Igumale region and provide clear pathways for sustainable resource exploration, responsible environmental management, and future energy development.

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6 Author contributions

Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Johnson U. Abangwu and Ngozi Agatha Okwesili: Conceptualization and Research design

Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Jude Chukwuebuka Ugwu, John Akor Yakubu and Okechukwu Desmond Ugbor: Field data acquisition and analysis.

Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Ngozi Agatha Okwesili, John Akor Yakubu, Johnson U. Abangwu and Emmanuel Awucha Igwe, Arewa James Ogahb, Ojobeagu Austin Okechukwu: Methodology, data interpretation and manuscript writing.

Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Jude Chukwuebuka Ugwu, Okechukwu Desmond Ugbor and Emmanuel Awucha Igwe: Reviewing, Editing and Supervision.

All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

7 Data availability

The data used in this manuscript will be made available if requested for.

8 Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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10 Compliance with ethical standards

No animals were used for this research; hence the research work complied with ethical standard.

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